

Automatic Layout Generation Based on GAN

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Abstract: Layout generation is to construct a proper combination by setting the location, size and other attributes of each layout element. Creative and visually attractive layouts are generally designed by excellent professional graphic designers. Yet, in the Internet era, it is challenging to keep up with the rapid growing requirement because the whole design process is heavily dependent on manual work and inefficient, and communication costs are expensive between Party A and designers. This paper mainly solves the problem of automatic layout generation in various graphic designs, including documents and images. Understanding the relationships between these graphic elements is necessary when designing a new layout or extending an existing layout. To achieve this, we propose a neural network model based on adversarial generative network and self-attention mechanism. It trains on real data samples, learns the distribution of samples, and is finally used for layout generation tasks. Based on LayoutGAN ++, we investigate the layout generation issue in graphic design, create a network structure that reflects its fundamentals, and theoretically analyze the model's generator, discriminator, and auxiliary decoder. Then, three data sets (Magazine, RICO, PubLayNet) were tested on the model, and on the basis of this, potential model optimization directions were explored. Experimental results demonstrate that our model can generate meaningful layouts in various layout generation application scenarios, such as mobile applications, documents, and magazine layout generation tasks.

Keywords: Automatic layout generation; GAN; Magazine; RICO; PubLayNet

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Introduction

Layout is the foundation of graphic design. Items such as magazine covers, advertising banners, and other objects contain layout information. Creative and visually attractive layouts are generally designed by excellent professional graphic designers. Yet, in the Internet era, it is challenging to keep up with the rapid growing requirement because the whole design process is heavily dependent on manual work and inefficient, and communication costs between Party A and designers are expensive.

It is conceivable to apply artificial intelligence technology to contribute to the design and production of graphic content in the context of the Internet's data explosion and the continual rise in computer processing capacity. In recent years, more and more large-scale data sets that can be used for graphic layout design research such as Magazine[22], RICO[2], WebForest[7] have come up. Industry and academia have made new progress in the automatic generation of layout by making full use of the most recent deep learning findings.

We evaluate the layout generation model by several different tasks, including Magazine, RICO and PubLayNet[23]. RICO provides UI layout design gathered from mobile applications, Magazine provides magazine page layout design, and PubLayNet provides document type layout design. In each case, our method successfully generates layouts related to the element types of the problem domain and their relationships. In summary, we train the generator in a suitable way, so that the generator can generate diverse and real data, and explores the possible optimization possibilities of the model on this basis.

Related Work

Automatic layout generation research has long been a common interest of both academics and business. Street networks, plots, floor plans, gaming levels, furniture and item layouts, shelves, and other fields have all been the topics of research in the past by academics who explored professional layouts. Several layouts generating approaches, including rule-based modeling[13], random search[12], and integer programming[17], have been proposed.

The deep generative model has become the primary research topic for automatic layout generation in recent years. Benefiting from the fast improvement of computer performance, learning the probability density of observable samples and randomly creating new sample generation models have become major hot topics. The deep generative model, in contrast to the classic generative model, combines deep learning and the generative model to produce a high capacity for learning sample distribution. A layout generation model based on the self-attention process was proposed by Gupta et al.[3]. The model is trained using an autoregressive method and leverages self-attention to capture the geometric and semantic links between parts. Similarly, Para et al. [16] solved the interior design arrangement using an autoregressive model and represented the relationship between elements using a graph. A model for generating scene layout based on variational autoencoder was proposed by Jyothi et al. [5], which employs descriptive statements to produce relevant layouts. The body layout generation of magazine article pages was studied by Zheng et al. [22] using conditional generative adversarial networks. To give users some degree of autonomy, keywords and images were encoded. Li et al. [9] proposed the LayoutGAN model to address the misalignment and occlusion defects of layout generation based on generative adversarial networks. The model was then enhanced to a conditional generative adversarial network with layout attributes as input [10]. LayoutGAN was improved by Kikuchi et al.[6] in an effort to make the model training process more stable. The potential vector is optimized to make the generated layout more attractive and to realize the relative relationships between the elements. The layout of elements with a tree-like relationship can be studied using the data set Webforest [7] which was published by Kikuchi et al. and proposed an optimization-based algorithm for processing hierarchical data.

Scene graph represents the relative positional relationship between elements. An important research topic is scene graph-based layout generation. Nauata et al. [14][15] produced an experiment for generating the indoor floor plan based on the generative adversarial network and used the scene graph to describe the layout of the interior floor plan of the house. Johnson et al. [4] used descriptive sentences to generate corresponding pictures. In order to generate tasks through relation completion, Lee et al. [8] introduced user constraints in layout generation based on relation graph, and continued to generate tasks through relation completion.

Research Methodology

Layout Representation

We employ the geometric characteristics of the element to convey the layout information rather from using the pixel-level image as the layout representation [22]. In particular, we use the values of w and h to indicate the height and width of the element and the values of x and y to describe the element's position. The normalized center coordinate, width, and height of the box are $[x_c, y_c, w, h]$.

Suppose there is a graphic layout composed of a set of N design elements, then all elements in the layout can be represented as the label set $L = \{l_1, \dots, l_N\}$, where L represents the class label of these elements, and the layout information of all elements in the layout can be represented by the set $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_N\}$.

Network Components

The network structure of the model, which is based on LayoutGAN ++ [6], is shown in Fig. 1. Generator, discriminator, and auxiliary decoder make up its three main components. Like the majority of GAN models, discriminator and auxiliary decoder are only used during model training, and subsequent applications only use the generated model component when doing generating tasks.

Fig. 1: Layout generative adversarial networks

The generator is shown in Fig. 1. The input of the generated model $G: (Z, L) \rightarrow B$ is composed of two parts: the hidden vector $Z: \{z_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and the label $L: \{l_i\}_{i=1}^N$. The output of the model is the bounding box representation of the element $B: \{b_i\}_{i=1}^N$. The number of a group of elements is indicated by the superscript N , and their order is indicated by the subscript i . The dataset determines the type of labels. There are 5 types of labels, for instance, in the MAGAZINE dataset: text, image, title, text floating image, and title floating image.

Information interaction between elements is essential. For example, it's common for layout elements to overlap, but we don't want a text element to be covered up by other elements. As a result, the generator's main body contains the attention mechanism. The main part of the generated model is the same as the encoder part in Transformer [21], and the only difference is the token encoding part. Its original text uses Transformer for sequence generation tasks, whose word encoding consists of tokens and corresponding position encodings. In the layout generation task, the token encoding is composed of tokens and a random vector z with normal distribution.

The interaction with the discriminator is the generator's most crucial learning method. Since the discriminator can access both real samples and generated samples, the generator can learn from the discriminator and imitate the data distribution of real samples to generate high quality counterfeits.

The discriminator model is shown in Fig. 1. The structure of the discriminator model is roughly the same as that of the

generated model. The difference lies in the input and output parts. The input of the discriminant model $D: (B, L) \rightarrow r$ consists of two parts: the bounding box of the element represents $\{b_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and the label $L: \{l_i\}_{i=1}^N$. The output of the model is a scalar value r , which is used to measure the veracity of the layout.

The self-supervision of the discriminator has been proved to be effective for stable generative adversarial network training[1][11][20]. The specific technique is to incorporate the idea of an autoencoder (AE) into a generative adversarial network. The discriminator model is viewed as the AE's encoder, and its output is viewed as the AE's low-dimensional vector. Based on this, a network is added, and it serves the same purpose as the decoder in AE, restoring the encoder's input.

The auxiliary decoder is shown in Fig. 1. The model forces the discriminator model to learn bounding box information and label information by the auxiliary decoder, and strengthens the sensitivity of the discriminator model to both, thus stabilizing the training of the whole model. The input of the auxiliary decoder has two parts. N copies of the hidden vector $h_{i=1}$ corresponding to the first element of the output of the discriminator model is used as the input of the auxiliary decoder. In addition, the learnable position code is input to the auxiliary encoder as another part. The output of the auxiliary encoder is the reconstructed bounding box $\hat{B}: \{\hat{b}_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and label $\hat{L}: \{\hat{l}_i\}_{i=1}^N$. The reconstruction loss can be obtained using the reconstructed bounding box and label information. By optimizing the network parameters to reduce the reconstruction loss, the discriminator model can be forced to learn bounding box information and label information.

Target and Loss Function

The model's objective function is based on the original generative adversarial network's objective function. and the objective function term of the auxiliary decoder is added. The total objective function of the model is shown as follows:

$$\min_{\theta} \max_{\phi, \xi} E_{(B,L) \sim P_{data}} [D(B, L; \phi) - \mathcal{L}_{rec}(B, L, \hat{B}(\theta, \xi), \hat{L}(\theta, \xi))] + E_{Z \sim N, L \sim P_{data}} [1 - D(G(Z, L; \theta), L; \phi)] \quad (1)$$

Among them, θ is the network parameter of the generator, ϕ is the network parameter of the discriminator, ξ is the network parameter of the auxiliary encoder, and \mathcal{L}_{rec} represents the reconstruction loss. The reconstruction loss measures the similarity between two sets of bounding boxes and labels. The bounding box reconstruction loss function and the label reconstruction loss function make up the reconstruction loss function.

The bounding box reconstruction loss function is as follows:

$$L_{MSE}(B, \hat{B}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (b_i' - b_i)}{N} \quad (2)$$

where N is the sample size, b_i is the bounding box representation of the element.

The label reconstruction loss function is as follows:

$$L_{cross}(L, \hat{L}) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M y_{ij} \log(p_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

where N is the sample size, M is the number of categories, y_{ij} is whether the category j is the real category of x_i , and p_{ij} is the prediction probability the instance x_i belongs to category j .

The loss function of the generator is as follows:

$$L_G = -D(G(Z, L)) \quad (4)$$

The loss function of the discriminator is as follows:

$$L_D = -D(B, L) + D(G(Z, L)) + \mathcal{L}_{rec}(B, L, \hat{B}, \hat{L}) \quad (5)$$

The discriminator will increase its capacity to distinguish between real and fake data as much as possible during the model's training process, and the generator will produce real data as much as possible. The discriminator uses real data along with false data to train and update the weights, while the generator can only use the error feedback obtained by the discriminator to update the weights. As the training progresses, the discriminator's discriminative capacity will be improved, which in turn forces the generator to generate more realistic samples. Finally, the generated samples should ideally be nearly identical to the real samples.

Evaluation Metrics

(1) FID

FID (Fréchet Inception Distance) is the most widely used GAN evaluation metric. In order to obtain the corresponding feature vectors, the generated samples and real samples are specifically input into the Inception network. The distance between the feature vectors represents the distribution difference between the generated samples and the real samples.

(2) Maximum IOU

IOU (Intersection over Union), a commonly used metric in the object detection, is used to evaluate how closely the predicted region and the target region match. We use a similar expression (bounding box) for the layout information in the layout generation task, allowing us to use IOU as the evaluation metric.

In contrast to the simple IOU, Maximum IOU is used to quantify the degree of correspondence between two bounding box sets. We specifically employ the Maximum IOU expression from earlier work [6].

(3) Overlap

Whether the elements in the layout can overlap is based on application scenarios and specific needs. In some cases, such as newspapers and documents, overlaps between any element pairs will be avoided as much as possible. In the layout of the magazine type, it is common for text to float above the picture, and we should avoid calculating overlapping losses in this case. Therefore, it is necessary to use different overlapping loss functions for specific layout types.

The loss function used to represent the degree of overlap between specified element pairs is shown as follows:

$$L_{overlap} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{\substack{\forall j \neq \\ \{i, skip(i)\}}} \frac{s_i \cap s_j}{s_i} \quad (6)$$

where $skip(i)$ is an artificially added rule based on a specific dataset. $skip(i)$ obtains the label of the element with the subscript i , and returns the subscript of the element corresponding to the label that does not calculate the overlap loss. $s_i \cap s_j$ corresponds to the overlap area between element i and element j .

(4) Alignment

The alignment between the elements is also important for the overall aesthetics of the layout. There are usually six possible alignment types between elements: left alignment, top alignment, right alignment, bottom alignment, center alignment in X and center alignment in Y , that is, $\theta = (xL, yT, xR, yB, xC, yC)$.

The loss function of the alignment between any element pairs in the layout is shown as follows.

$$L_{alignment} = \sum_{i=1}^N \min \left(g(\Delta x_i^L), g(\Delta x_i^C), g(\Delta x_i^R), g(\Delta x_i^T), g(\Delta x_i^B), g(\Delta x_i^C) \right) \quad (7)$$

where $g(x) = -\log(1 - x)$, and $\Delta x_i^* (* = L, C, R)$ is calculated by the follows:

$$\Delta x_i^* = \min_{\forall j \neq i} |x_i^* - x_j^*| \quad (8)$$

Similarly, Δy_i^* can be obtained.

Datasets and Experimental Settings

The experimental environment is pytorch1.11.0 + cuda113 deep learning framework with Adam optimizer. The word vector dimension (d_{model}) in Transformer is set to 256, the number of multi-head self-attention attention heads (n_{head}) is set to 8, and the number of model layers is set to 4. The above settings are the same as the generator, discriminator and auxiliary encoder. The optimizer of the model is AdamW, the learning rate is 1e-05, and the training batch batch is set to 64. The number of training iterations is 300,000.

For the PubLayNet dataset, we use the official dataset segmentation method for training, validating, and testing. For the Rico and Magazine datasets, since the data is not officially segmented, we use 85 % of the dataset for training, 5 % for validating, and 10 % for testing.

Results and Discussions

Baseline Model Results

Fig. 2 displays the experimental findings based on the Magazine dataset. The figure shows that although there is a slight misalignment and overlap between the layout elements, the model has high quality results that are closer to the real data distribution.

Fig. 3 displays the experimental outcomes based on the Publaynet dataset. The results shown in the figure are generally in line with Magazine, and because document type data naturally aligns elements in the generated layout, this is also apparent in the $l_{alignment}$ item in Table 1.

Fig. 4 displays the experiment results based on the Rico dataset. The Rico dataset differs from the first two datasets in that there is a lot of white space (the elements don't occupy the entire layout space) and a lot of overlap between the elements, which is also apparent in the figure. The model accurately picks up on this type of data distribution.

Table 1: Quality evaluation of experimental results on three datasets

dataset	FID	Max_iou	$l_{alignment}$	$l_{overlap}$
Magazine	12.12	0.265	0.333	0.181
Publaynet	23.12	0.336	0.087	0.156
Rico	15.31	0.366	0.225	0.625

Fig. 2: Examples of experimental results for the Magazine dataset

Fig. 3: Examples of experimental results for the Publaynet dataset

Fig. 4: Examples of experimental results for the Rico dataset

From the above experimental analysis, it can be seen that model can indeed learn the data distribution pattern of the layout to a certain extent, but compared with the distribution of the original data, there are some misalignments and overlaps in the generated layout, which needs to be further improved in future work.

Contrast Experiments

We employ a variety of methods to modify the fundamental model [6] in order to achieve the best settings. The test set of the Magazine data set is the foundation for the experimental data. The experimental results are shown in Table 2. The effects of the model before and after the auxiliary decoder ablation, the effects of various d_{model} values on the model,

the effects of various n_{head} values on the model, and the effects of various Transformer block layers on the model were all compared in this experiment.

Table 2: Comparative experiments between different model variants *

	N_{layer}	d_{model}	n_{head}	FID ↓	Max_iou ↑	$l_{alignment}$ $\times 10^2$ ↓	$l_{overlap}$ ↓	$Params$ $\times 10^5$	$Time_{avg}$ $\times 10^{-4}$
Baseline	8	256	4	12.12	0.265	0.333	0.181	27.1	8.3
(A)	2			12.73	0.245	0.387	0.260	7.2	5.1
	4			11.88	0.252	0.301	0.202	13.9	5.8
	6			12.66	0.247	0.281	0.187	20.5	5.7
	10			17.41	0.258	0.316	0.186	33.6	7.3
	12			12.56	0.262	0.355	0.139	40.3	8.7
(B)		64		12.82	0.250	0.354	0.265	1.7	6.2
		128		11.50	0.260	0.367	0.211	6.8	6.4
		512		26.52	0.232	0.359	0.345	108	7.2
(C)			2	14.19	0.254	0.272	0.251	27.1	7.6
			8	12.38	0.263	0.305	0.154	27.1	6.7
			16	14.44	0.268	0.311	0.151	27.1	6.6
(D)	Without auxiliary decoder			20.50	0.248	0.362	0.233	27.1	6.8
(E)	e1	4	8	11.09	0.267	0.269	0.163	13.9	5.6
	e2	4	128	12.76	0.252	0.370	0.217	3.5	5.4
	e3		128	11.22	0.255	0.351	0.174	6.8	6.3
	e4	4	128	12.01	0.256	0.336	0.185	3.5	5.6
	e5	6		8	11.27	0.260	0.333	0.139	20.5

Note*: N_{layer} represents the number of Transformer block layers. ↑ indicates that the larger the metric, the better, ↓ indicates that the smaller the metric, the better.

Ablation of Auxiliary Decoder

The self-monitoring mechanism, auxiliary decoder for the discriminator model, is introduced into the network to stabilize the training of the entire model by forcing the discriminator model to learn the bounding box information and label information through the auxiliary decoder and strengthening its sensitivity to both. The auxiliary decoder's role can be determined by an ablation experiment.

As shown in Table 2(D), the removal of the auxiliary encoder reduces the FID from 12.12 to 20.50, and the Max_IOW from 0.265 to 0.241, and the loss values of alignment and overlap also increase. The changes of each metric show that removing the auxiliary encoder will greatly reduce the training effect of the generated model.

Model Variations

(1) d_{model}

High-dimensional feature vectors are needed in neural networks for information transmission. The model's feature vector dimension is assigned as d_{model} . Different d_{model} value in the experiment have an effect on how well the model performs.

Table 2(B) demonstrates that as the feature vector dimension increases, the model's overall performance tends to rise initially until declining. Fig. 5 displays the relationship between d_{model} and model performance. It demonstrates that when the d_{model} value is 128 or 256, the model's overall performance is higher.

Fig. 5: The correlation between d_{model} and model performance

(2) n_{head}

Multiple Transformer blocks, including a multi-head attention network, make up the main portion of the generator, discriminator, and auxiliary encoder. The number of attention heads in the multi-head attention network is assigned as n_{head} . Different n_{head} value in the experiment have an effect on the model's overall performance.

Fig. 6: The correlation between n_{head} and model performance

Table 2(C) demonstrates that as the feature n_{head} value increases, the model's overall performance tends to rise initially until declining. Fig. 6 displays the relationship between n_{head} value and model performance. It demonstrates that when the n head value is 4 or 8, the model's overall performance is higher.

(3) N_{layer}

Transformer Blocks make up the main portion of the generator, discriminator, and auxiliary encoder. The depth of the network model is determined by N_{layer} , the number of layers of the Transformer Block.

Table 4(A) demonstrates that as the N_{layer} value increases, the model's overall performance tends to rise initially until declining. Fig. 7 displays the relationship between the N_{layer} value and model performance. It demonstrates that when N_{layer} is 4 or 6 or 8, the model's overall performance is higher.

Fig. 7: The correlation between N_{layer} and model performance

(4) Multi-factor

To find out the perfect model settings (as described in Section 4.1), we implement a large number of controlled experiments. In this section, the test results using the above model settings are shown in e1 of Table 2(E). Fig. 8 displays the outcomes of the multi-factor comparison experiments. when the four indicators are combined, the model outperforms the baseline model (original layoutGAN++) in terms of overall performance.

Fig. 8: Multi-factor contrast experiment

Conclusion

LayoutGAN++ is selected as baseline of our model. Firstly, its generator, discriminator and auxiliary decoder are analyzed theoretically. Finally, experiments are carried out on three data sets and experimental results are obtained. The experiment verifies that the model has the layout generation ability and versatility under unconstrained conditions.

In addition, our model has made a small amount of optimization compared to the original LayoutGAN ++, according to a number of comparative experiments, comparisons, and analysis of various model variants.

The experimental results prove that the generative adversarial network can be used to learn the data distribution of the layout and realize the generation of unconstrained layout, which highlights its wide application in the field of graphic design.

Automatic generation of graphic layout represents only a small portion of the implementation of intelligent design. There is a lot more work to be done before intelligent graphic design can truly be realized. The layout generation algorithm still needs more work. In the research on GAN-based graphic layout generation, there has been a problem with the misalignment and occlusion between elements not being sensitive enough. One potential solution is the use of bounding box rendering[9], but we were unable to replicate them. Although there are some additional techniques[6] to reduce misalignment and occlusion, doing so will increase the time cost of layout generation.

The 'content' of the elements is not considered when creating the layout. For both images and text, existing research has been able to achieve powerful feature extraction capabilities[18][19]. However, the "content" of the elements is frequently disregarded in the existing research on layout generation, and only the label is used to represent the category of elements. For instance, when an element is a background element in the layout, the model only understands that it needs to arrange an object that belongs to "background " and incorrectly arranges other elements according to the content of the background image (such as blanks, etc.). A top-notch graphic design automation tool should be able to take the "content" into consideration.

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